

A Hybrid Learning-based Model for Predicting Diabetes using Tabular Network

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Abstract—Diabetes mellitus, a metabolic disorder characterized by hyperglycemia, poses a significant global health burden. Early and accurate diagnosis of diabetes subtypes is crucial for effective management and prevention of complications. This research addresses the challenge of multi-class diabetes type prediction using a local dataset. A deep learning approach, specifically Tabular Network, is employed to classify patients into different diabetes types. Tabular Network unique sequential attention mechanism dynamically selects relevant features at each decision step, enhancing model performance. Experimental results demonstrated the superiority of Tabular Network over other machine learning algorithms like Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Boosting and logistic regression. This research contributes to the advancement of diabetes diagnosis and offers a promising tool for healthcare professionals to make informed clinical decisions.

Keywords— *Diabetes prediction, Multi-class classification, Tabular Network, Machine Learning*

I. INTRODUCTION

Diabetes Mellitus, commonly referred to as diabetes, is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by prolonged elevated blood sugar levels. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), this condition arises either from insufficient insulin secretion by the pancreas or the body's ineffective response to insulin [3]. The prevalence of diabetes is increasing globally, and its impact is particularly severe in developing countries like Nigeria. If left unmanaged, diabetes can lead to serious complications affecting the heart, eyes, kidneys, and nervous system, significantly increasing the risk of premature mortality.

There are primarily two types of chronic diabetes: Type 1 Diabetes (T1D) and Type 2 Diabetes (T2D). T1D, often referred to as insulin-dependent or juvenile diabetes, typically manifests in younger individuals, often below the age of 30. This condition requires continuous insulin therapy as it cannot be managed with oral medications [1]. Conversely, T2D, previously termed non-insulin-dependent diabetes, is more common in middle-aged and older adults. This type of diabetes is frequently associated with lifestyle factors such as obesity, hypertension, and dyslipidemia [2]. Additionally, there are transient forms of diabetes, including gestational diabetes, which occurs during pregnancy, and prediabetes, a condition characterized by higher-than-normal blood glucose levels that may progress to diabetes without intervention.

The global rise in diabetes is partly driven by urbanization, economic development, and lifestyle changes.

These trends highlight the critical need for effective diagnostic and management tools [3]. Machine learning (ML) has emerged as a transformative technology in this regard, offering the potential to enhance the early prediction and classification of chronic diseases, including diabetes. ML algorithms can analyze vast datasets to identify patterns and make accurate predictions, which are crucial for early intervention and reducing the burden on healthcare systems [1].

Despite numerous advances in ML applications for healthcare, significant challenges remain. Traditional studies on diabetes prediction have predominantly focused on binary classification models that distinguish between diabetic and non-diabetic individuals [3]. However, these approaches fail to address the nuanced needs of healthcare professionals, who require detailed insights into the specific type of diabetes a patient has. Distinguishing between T1D, T2D, and gestational diabetes is essential for tailoring treatment plans and improving patient outcomes. Moreover, the application of advanced models such as TabNet, a deep learning architecture specifically designed for tabular data, remains underexplored in this context [4].

TabNet leverages a unique sequential attention mechanism, which allows it to focus on the most relevant features during each decision step, providing interpretability alongside robust predictive performance [2]. Unlike conventional ML models, TabNet's architecture can handle complex, high-dimensional datasets typical in medical research, making it well-suited for the multi-class classification of diabetes. The model's ability to highlight important features enhances its utility in clinical settings, where understanding the basis of predictions can inform better medical decision-making [5].

The Nigerian healthcare system is increasingly relying on electronic health records (EHRs) to store and manage patient data. This presents a unique opportunity to develop and deploy advanced predictive models like TabNet. However, there remains a gap in the systematic application of such models to local datasets, particularly for multi-class classification tasks involving diverse patient demographics. Existing studies in Nigeria have largely used simpler classification techniques and limited datasets, which restrict their generalizability and efficacy [3]. Addressing this gap by applying TabNet to predict different types of diabetes could significantly enhance diagnostic accuracy and treatment planning in resource-constrained settings.

In this study, we aim to develop a robust predictive model using TabNet to classify diabetes into four categories: T1D, T2D, gestational diabetes, and healthy individuals. Unlike previous approaches that combine multiple machine learning models, this study focuses solely on TabNet to maximize its feature selection capabilities. The model will be evaluated against established benchmarks, including other state-of-the-art algorithms such as Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs), ensemble methods and logistic regression, to demonstrate its superiority in terms of accuracy and interpretability.

The ultimate goal of this research is to empower healthcare practitioners with a reliable tool for early diabetes detection and classification, thereby improving patient care. By leveraging locally sourced datasets and focusing on multi-class classification, this study not only bridges existing gaps in diabetes prediction research but also contributes to the global effort of enhancing healthcare outcomes through advanced technologies.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Studies on Binary and Multi-Class Classification of Diabetes

Research on diabetes prediction has predominantly focused on binary classification, distinguishing diabetic from non-diabetic individuals. For instance [1] employed several machine learning classifiers, including RF, SVM, and Decision Tree, achieving an accuracy of 95.20% in binary diabetes prediction. Similarly, [2] used data mining techniques to predict diabetes using Logistic Regression, SVM, and Naïve Bayes, with the Logistic Regression model achieving an accuracy of 82.46%. However, while binary classification models offer insights into the presence or absence of diabetes, they fall short in guiding specific treatment options for different diabetes types.

Recent studies have started exploring multi-class classification to provide a more detailed analysis. [6] applied Multinomial Logistic Regression, Artificial Neural Networks (ANN), and RF to classify metabolic conditions into three categories, achieving a weighted average accuracy of 81.50%. This multi-class approach is essential as it offers a nuanced understanding of the disease, distinguishing between Type 1, Type 2, and gestational diabetes.

B. Ensemble Learning Approaches in Diabetes Prediction

Ensemble learning combines multiple algorithms to improve predictive performance, leveraging their individual strengths. The authors in [4] adopted an ensemble approach by combining SVM, RF, and XGBoost to classify diabetes into three categories: Type 1, Type 2, and no diabetes. Using data from Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital, the ensemble model achieved an accuracy of 90%. This dataset forms the basis of our study, emphasizing the potential of ensemble techniques to enhance diagnostic accuracy. Saidu

III. METHODOLOGY

This section outlines the structured approach adopted for developing a robust machine learning model to predict diabetes as shown in Fig. 2. The proposed methodology emphasizes a deep learning framework optimized for tabular data. Although principal component analysis

et al.'s [4] methodology demonstrates how integrating different algorithms can yield robust models capable of handling complex, high-dimensional datasets.

Another notable study by [9] implemented a Bayesian-optimized TabNet model for binary diabetes classification. The model achieved an accuracy of 92.2% and highlighted TabNet's interpretability through SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) values, which elucidate the contribution of each feature to the model's predictions. This study underscores the utility of TabNet in medical diagnostics, providing insights into feature importance and facilitating model transparency.

C. Deep Learning Models for Tabular Data

Deep learning models, particularly those designed for tabular data, have shown promise in healthcare applications. TabNet, introduced by [7], is a deep learning architecture tailored for tabular datasets. Its unique sequential attention mechanism enables it to focus on the most salient features at each decision step, offering both high performance and interpretability. [6] further extended TabNet by incorporating spatial attention, enhancing its performance in hyperspectral image classification. This demonstrates TabNet's adaptability across different domains, including healthcare.

Despite its potential, TabNet's application in multi-class diabetes classification remains limited. Existing studies primarily focus on binary outcomes, as seen in works by [8], who used deep neural networks for binary classification of diabetes, achieving an accuracy of 98.97%. However, these models often lack interpretability, a critical factor in medical applications where understanding the rationale behind predictions is essential for clinical decision-making.

D. Gaps in Current Research

While significant advancements have been made in diabetes prediction using ML and deep learning, several gaps persist. First, most studies focus on binary classification, overlooking the clinical need to differentiate between various types of diabetes. Accurate identification of diabetes type is crucial for personalized treatment, as the management strategies for Type 1, Type 2, and gestational diabetes differ significantly [10]. Second, the integration of advanced deep learning models like TabNet in multi-class classification tasks is underexplored, particularly in the context of locally sourced datasets. This gap is evident in the study by [4], which used ANN and decision trees for binary diabetes classification on a Nigerian dataset but did not extend the analysis to multi-class scenarios.

Moreover, while ensemble methods have shown promise, as demonstrated by [3], their application in real-world clinical settings requires further validation. The study highlighted the importance of feature importance analysis in improving model interpretability, a crucial aspect that has not been adequately addressed in many existing works.

(PCA) is typically used to enhance feature selection and reduce dimensionality, it has been excluded in this study. Instead, a purely TabNet-based approach is employed, leveraging its interpretability and efficiency for handling tabular datasets. Table 1 shows the number of variables considered in this research.

Fig. 2: Research Workflow

A. Data Collection

The dataset for this research was sourced from the Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital (ABUTH), Shika, Zaria. The data includes comprehensive patient records with demographic and clinical attributes relevant to diabetes diagnosis. Features in the dataset include:

- Demographic data: Age, gender, and number of pregnancies.
- Clinical measurements: Body Mass Index (BMI), fasting blood sugar (FBS), glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c), two-hour postprandial plasma glucose (2HPP), and high-density lipoprotein (HDL).

Table 1 provides an overview of the attributes included in the diabetes dataset, which is specifically tailored to the Nigerian context. This dataset comprises thirteen distinct attributes, each carefully selected for its relevance to diabetes research. The primary objective of this study is to classify diabetes into different types, making it the central target variable.

Table 1: Number of variables

S/N	Attributes	Data Type
0	Age	Int64
1	Sex	Object
2	FH (DM)	Object
3	SmokingST	Object
4	No of Preg	Int64
5	Height (m)	Float64
6	Weight (kg)	Float64
7	BMI	Float64
8	HbA1c	Float64
9	Fast Plasma-FBS(mmol/l)	Float64
10	Fast Plasma-2HPP(mmol/l)	Float64
11	HDL	Float64
12	Type of DM	Object

B. Data Preprocessing

The initial stage of this research involved rigorous data preprocessing to ensure the quality and suitability of the diabetes dataset for model development. Several key steps were undertaken to prepare the data:

Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA): A comprehensive EDA was conducted to understand the dataset's characteristics, identify patterns, and uncover potential insights. This analysis revealed the need for data cleaning, normalization, and handling missing values.

Handling Missing Data: To address missing values, a K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) imputation technique was employed. This method effectively filled in missing data points by identifying similar data instances and imputing the most probable value.

Normalization: To prevent attributes with larger ranges from dominating the analysis, normalization was applied. Min-max normalization was used to scale the values of the weight and BMI attributes to a specific range, ensuring that all attributes contribute equally to the model.

Data Splitting and Validation: The dataset was divided into training and testing sets, with 80% allocated for training and 20% for testing. This split allowed for model training and subsequent evaluation on unseen data.

C. Model Development

The TabNet model, a powerful deep learning architecture, is employed to classify diabetes types based on the extracted features. This model excels in handling tabular data by sequentially attending to relevant features at each decision step. By doing so, TabNet efficiently learns from the most salient information in the data and enhances interpretability.

The input dataset are fed into the TabNet model as shown in Figure 3, which then progresses through a series of feature selection steps. TabNet's ability to handle high-dimensional data and its unique feature selection mechanism are crucial for identifying the most important factors contributing to diabetes classification. The model's sparsity control further optimizes the learning process by focusing on the most relevant features.

A sequential decision-making process is employed, where information is passed between steps to refine the classification. Feature transformers are used to process the data effectively, while ghost batch normalization ensures efficient training. Finally, a decision tree-like aggregation mechanism is used to make accurate classifications.

Through the capabilities of TabNet, our model is able to effectively extract complex patterns from the diabetes data, leading to improved accuracy in diabetes type classification. This approach provides a valuable tool for healthcare professionals to make informed decisions and develop effective treatment strategies.

Fig. 3: TabNet Encoder used for Modeling Diabetes

D. Model Training and Optimization

The TabNet model was trained using the Adam optimizer, a popular choice for its efficient convergence and ability to handle sparse gradients. To further enhance the training process, a learning rate scheduler was employed. This scheduler dynamically adjusts the learning rate during training, allowing for more effective optimization.

Given the multi-class nature of the diabetes classification problem, a categorical cross-entropy loss function was utilized. This loss function measures the discrepancy between the predicted class probabilities and the true class labels.

To prevent overfitting, an early stopping mechanism was implemented. This technique monitors the validation performance and terminates the training process when the performance stops improving. This helps to avoid overfitting and ensures that the model generalizes well to unseen data.

E. Model Evaluation

The performance of the TabNet model was assessed using a range of metrics:

- Accuracy: Overall proportion of correctly classified instances.
- Precision: Proportion of true positive predictions for each class.
- Recall: Proportion of actual positives correctly identified.
- F1-score: Harmonic mean of precision and recall, providing a balanced performance measure.
- Log Loss: Evaluates the confidence of predictions.

Additionally, a confusion matrix was generated to provide insight into the distribution of errors across classes.

F. Tools and Environment

The following tools were utilized:

- Python: Primary programming language.
- Scikit-learn: For data preprocessing and evaluation metrics.
- Pandas and NumPy: For data manipulation and analysis.
- PyTorch: For implementing the TabNet model.
- Matplotlib and Seaborn: For visualization.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the outcomes of the experimental evaluations conducted in this study. Table 2 present the comparison of the analysis.

Table 2: Comparison Analysis

Model	Model	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Logloss
Proposed TabNet Model	TabNet	94.03%	93%	95%	94%	0.15
Saidu et al. (2024)	Ensemble Soft Voting	85%	87%	85%	85%	0.35
Evwiekpaefe & Abdulkadir (2023)	ANN	88.8%	89%	89%	88%	0.17
Rastogi & Bansal (2023)	Logistic Regression	82.46%	0.90	0.68	0.83	

The TabNet model demonstrated superior performance across all metrics, underscoring its effectiveness for multi-class classification of diabetes types. Notably, it outperformed the ensemble soft voting approach of [4] and the ANN model by [11].

A. Analysis of Misclassifications

Despite achieving high overall accuracy, the TabNet model exhibited a few misclassifications, particularly between the healthy class and Type 2 diabetes. Such errors are likely due to overlapping clinical features, including blood glucose levels, which present similarly across these classes. Table 3 provides a detailed breakdown of the misclassification rates for each class:

Table 3 Detailed breakdown of the misclassification rates for each class

Class	Misclassified Instances	Possible Causes
Healthy	5	Overlapping glucose levels
Type 1 Diabetes	3	Similar clinical markers with Type 2 diabetes
Type 2 Diabetes	7	Overlap with healthy and Type 1 diabetes
Gestational Diabetes	2	Outlier cases or unique feature variability

These insights emphasize the importance of incorporating domain knowledge to further refine the

model's ability to distinguish between closely related classes.

V. CONCLUSION

This research set out to develop a predictive model for diabetes classification, leveraging the capabilities of TabNet, a deep learning architecture tailored for tabular data. The primary objective was to accurately classify patients into one of four categories: healthy, Type 1 diabetes, Type 2 diabetes, and gestational diabetes. The study demonstrated the potential of TabNet in delivering high-performance outcomes, achieving an accuracy of 94.03% alongside robust precision, recall, and F1-scores across all classes.

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